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ЭПИЛЕПСИЯ ПРИ БЕРЕМЕННОСТИ ПРОГНОЗЫ И ЕГО ТЕЧЕНИЯ (ЛИТЕРАТУРНЫЙ ОБЗОР)

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Планирование беременности – наиболее ответственный период при эпилептическом синдроме. Необходимо подготовить организм, чтобы избежать приступов эпилепсии у беременных. Забеременеть и родить при эпилепсии можно только в период стойкой ремиссии. Редкие приступы, не чаще раза в полгода, можно считать таким периодом.

Ключевые слова: эпилепсия, беременность, женщины, судорги, пароксизмы

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EPILEPSY IN MATERNITY PROGNOSIS AND ITS COURSE (LITERATURE REVIEW)

ANNOTATION

Planning pregnancy is the most responsible period in epilepsy syndrome. It is necessary to prepare the body to avoid epileptic attacks in pregnant women. It is possible to become pregnant and give birth in epilepsy only in the period of persistent remission. Rare seizures, not more than once in six months, can be considered such a period.

Keywords: epilepsy, pregnancy, women, seizures, paroxysms

Djurabekova Surayyo Tohirovna

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HOMILADORLIKDAGI EPILEPSIYANING BASHORATLARI VA UNING KECHISHI (ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI)

ANNOTATSIYA

Homiladorlikni rejalashtirish epileptik sindrom uchun eng muhim davr hisoblanadi. Homilador ayollarda epilepsiya tutilishining oldini olish uchun tanani tayyorlash kerak. Epilepsiya bilan homilador bo'lish va tug'ish faqat doimiy remissiya davrida mumkin. Kamdan kam hujumlar, olti oyda bir martadan ko'p bo'lmagan holda, bunday davr deb hisoblanishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: epilepsiya, homiladorlik, ayollar, sudorglar, paroksizmalar

Introduction. Epileptic disease is a polyethological disease, and each of the factors plays only a predisposing role. In 86% of patients, paroxysmal syndrome develops before conception and is not associated with the effect of specific gestational changes. epilepsy can occur in women with congenital failure of brain structures caused by defects in neuronal differentiation, impaired neuronal migration, cortical dysgenesis, dysontogenesis, intrauterine neuroinfections, birth injuries. acquired predisposition is formed against the background of brain destruction after severe injuries, meningoencephalitis, strokes. Two thirds of the cases are hereditary [1]. In 98% of patients with idiopathic epileptic disease, the disorder has a polygenic basis and develops against the background of channelopathy, leading to instability of neuronal membranes, 1-2% of sick women convulsive syndrome is a manifestation of monogenic diseases in which protein, fat, carbohydrate metabolism is disrupted or degenerative changes of the nervous system occur: paroxysmal seizures are observed with lipofuscinosis, neurofibromatosis, progressive myoclonus-epilepsy, tuberous sclerosis, phenylketonuria, etc.[2]. In 14% of cases, seizures occur for the first time in pregnant women with prerequisites for the development of paroxysms, and are repeated only in subsequent gestations, which makes it justified to isolate gestational epilepsy as a separate form of the

disease. in such women, specific changes occurring during gestation contribute to the actualization of the clinical picture:

- changes in water-electrolyte metabolism. in pregnant women, the volume of circulating blood increases and the permeability of membranes increases, which contributes to the accumulation of fluids in tissues, including the brain. A physiological increase in ACTH levels contributes to the retention of sodium and chlorides. against the background of hypersecretion of mineralocorticoids, the content of calcium and magnesium decreases. The result of these changes is an increase in the excitability of cell membranes [3].

- hormonal adjustment. an increase in the convulsive readiness of brain tissue during gestation leads to a more than 30-fold increase in the concentration of estrogens. according to the results of research in the field of neurology, estrogenic stimulation increases the excitability of nerve cells. in some pregnant women, the anticonvulsive effect of progestins, whose level increases 10-fold, is insufficient to compensate for the action of estrogens[4]. Despite the high diaphragm position, pregnant women have increased pulmonary ventilation — the volume of inhaled and exhaled air increases by 40%, alveolar gas exchange accelerates, and the total lung resistance decreases by 2 times. against the background of hyperventilation, the concentration of carbon dioxide

in the blood decreases, which leads to narrowing of cerebral vessels, insufficient blood supply to brain cells and a decrease in their excitability threshold [5].

The situation is often aggravated by stress and emotional changes typical for pregnant women. Insufficient rest and sleep contribute to the accumulation of epileptogenic substances, and hormonal anxiety, irritability, a tendency to mood swings, panic reactions to changing well-being affect the reactivity of the central nervous system [6].

Pathogenesis: the mechanism of development of epilepsy in pregnant women is based on increased excitability of neuronal membranes and an imbalance of excitation-inhibition processes. Electrolyte shifts caused by gestational factors, disruption of membrane channels, sinuses, excitatory and inhibitory receptors affect neuronal activity and increase the convulsive readiness of brain tissues. The effect of super-threshold factors (strong emotional experience, peak increase in estrogen levels, and other external and internal stimuli) causes periodic focal depolarization of the membranes of neurons with the formation of a focus of epileptic activity. Further generalization of the process leads to the occurrence of convulsive and non-convulsive seizures [7].

Symptoms of epilepsy in pregnant women the clinic of paroxysms during gestation depends on the localization of the epileptogenic focus and the characteristics of the propagation of the excitation wave to various structures of the brain. With classic generalized convulsive seizures lasting up to 3 minutes, the pregnant woman loses consciousness, falls, she has a strong tonic contraction of the muscles of the body with subsequent convulsive convulsions of the muscles of the extremities, possible biting of the tongue, involuntary urination, sometimes defecation. At the end of the attack, consciousness does not recover immediately, breathing remains intermittent for some time, cyanotic and moist skin are characteristic, maximum pupil dilation without reaction to light. Sleep often follows a convulsive paroxysm [8].

In some patients, the seizure is preceded by an aura in the form of dizziness, chest tightness, illusory or hallucinatory olfactory, tactile, sound, auditory, gustatory sensations, motor automatism (scratching, sorting things, stomping on the spot, etc.). Some components may be missing in the structure of epileptic paroxysm. Thus, absences are manifested by short-term loss of consciousness without convulsive muscle contractions, and the most common partial seizures are tonic or clonic seizures, somatosensory disorders, vegetative-visceral manifestations (sweating, redness of the face, discomfort in the epigastrium, changes in pupil diameter) with preserved or altered consciousness. In rare cases, there are psychotic variants of epilepsy with a twilight state, hallucinations, delirium, dysphoric maliciously sad affect [9].

Complications: in 10-15% of pregnant women suffering mainly from post-traumatic and rheumatic epilepsy, seizures become more frequent, especially in the first and third trimesters. The progressive course of the disease is associated with the risk of developing an epileptic status, in which the maternal mortality rate reaches 16-20%, and perinatal mortality is 6.6%. 28.8% of patients with epilepsy develop late gestosis, including eclampsia, and 4-11% have premature birth. With epileptic disease, the risk of stillbirth, spontaneous abortions, and violent labor increases. In 16.9% of cases, early postpartum bleeding develops and in 28.4% — late. Pregnant women with paroxysms are 1.5 times more likely to have a cesarean section [5].

Traumatization, the risk of which increases in the presence of generalized seizures, increases the likelihood of intracerebral hemorrhages and fetal hydrocephalus. Up to 6-8% of children have congenital malformations, which is associated with the teratogenic effect of antiepileptic drugs that affect the folate cycle. Cleavage of the palate (cleft lip), spine (spina bifida), facial skull defects, heart defects are more common than others.

Epileptologists have described a specific embryonic aep syndrome in newborns, manifested by ptosis, strabismus, hypertelorism, epicanthus, flattened bridge of the nose, hypoplasia of nails and/or phalanges of fingers.

With the hereditary form of epilepsy in the mother, the probability of developing the disease in the child reaches 10%, with symptomatic forms of paroxysmal disease — 3-4% (against 1% on average in the

population). Intrauterine hypoxia occurs in 10.4% of fetuses, up to 23.2% of children are born in a state of asphyxia. Sometimes, against the background of taking anticonvulsants, a child develops erythroblastosis. 7-10% of newborns have a weight of less than 2,500 g. Also, children born to women with epilepsy usually have lower values on the Apgar scale. Perinatal mortality is 1.2-2 times higher than the average [8].

Diagnosis: difficulties in making a diagnosis are possible with the onset of epilepsy during pregnancy, especially if the paroxysms are convulsive. In such cases, the diagnostic search is aimed at detecting pathological neuronal activity in the brain, detecting the organic substrate of the disease, and assessing the prevalence of the pathological process. The most informative methods are: electroencephalography. The EEG study makes it possible to identify characteristic focal peak-wave complexes or asymmetric slow waves, as well as accurately localize a pathological cerebral focus. To increase the information content of the examination, it is possible to perform video EEG monitoring and assign functional tests (except hyperventilation).

MRI. Layered scanning of brain tissues allows you to detect structural changes (cerebral aneurysms, cavernous hemangiomas, arteriovenous malformations, cysts, neoplasia, hemorrhages, post-traumatic injuries) that contribute to the occurrence of paroxysms. MRI of the brain is effective for the diagnosis of symptomatic epilepsy [8].

Taking into account the possible violation of the folate cycle, pregnant women taking anticonvulsants are recommended to dynamically assess the content of folic acid, vitamin B12, homocysteine in blood serum. To exclude fetal abnormalities, prenatal screening is required: genetic ultrasound, consultation with a geneticist no later than the 17th week of gestational age, according to indications, the use of invasive diagnostic methods: chorion biopsy, cordocentesis, amniocentesis. Taking into account the risk of intrauterine hypoxia and delayed development of the child, ultrasound of uteroplacental blood flow, fetometry, CTG, phonocardiography of the fetus are recommended. Epilepsy in pregnant women is a chronic hereditary, congenital or acquired cerebral pathology that is caused by excessive neural activity and occurred before or during gestation. It is usually manifested by convulsive and convulsive paroxysms with or without loss of consciousness, less often by psychotic disorders in the form of twilight states, delirium, hallucinations, dysphoria. It is diagnosed using EEG, magnetic resonance imaging of the brain. For the treatment and prevention of possible complications, antiepileptic drugs, tranquilizers, folic acid, vitamins K1, D, B, sedative phytopreparations are used.

Epilepsy is a serious neurological disease that can lead to life-threatening seizures. Pathology imposes restrictions on people's daily lives, making certain things impossible or dangerous for them. In any course of the disease, at the stage of planning and preparing for conception, it is necessary:

- undergo a full health examination, treat concomitant diseases;
- spend a lot of time outdoors;
- avoid physical and emotional overwork;
- avoid stress;
- adhere to proper nutrition with the necessary changes in epileptic syndrome;

- eliminate alcohol, smoking, and avoid caffeinated beverages;
- get enough sleep

Danger to the child

If the mother does not have epilepsy attacks during pregnancy, then the consequences for the child that manifest themselves after birth will be insignificant. However, the presence of even mild seizures can lead to the death of the baby and mother, severe fetal pathologies.

The most dangerous condition is epistatus, in which seizures follow one another without stopping. In such a case, the woman should be taken to the hospital immediately, as there is a serious risk of miscarriage. Or oxygen starvation of the pregnant woman and fetus, leading to pathology of the brain, kidneys. The percentage of maternal mortality in this condition is 15-20%.

The second most important factor is the disease variant. If the seizures are of the focal type, that is, the flash affects small parts of the brain, there is practically no danger. Generalized seizures, involving extensive areas of neurons, seriously affect the intrauterine development of the baby, leading to pathologies of varying severity.

Severe consequences include: the development of hereditary epilepsy in the fetus, the chance of this is small, from 4 to 10%, but significantly higher than in initially healthy parents;

The wolf's mouth;

- harelip;
- pathology of the genital organs;
- heart defects;
- intestinal atresia;
- splitting of the spinal column.

Minor defects that do not even require surgical intervention:

- low location of the auricles;
- big mouth;
- underdevelopment of the phalanges of the fingers;
- underdevelopment of the nail plate.

Anticonvulsant drugs for epilepsy, taken before, during and after pregnancy, play the greatest role in the formation of abnormalities in babies. Because of them, the risk of giving birth to a sick baby increases dramatically.

Preventive examinations of such a pregnant woman are required more often, she is observed simultaneously by a gynecologist, a neurologist, and a geneticist.

A woman undergoes typical examinations, but a number of specific ones are added to the routine list:

- from week 12, a hormone level test is mandatory on a regular basis; ultrasound examination is done more often, in each of the important periods of gestation: for the first time, a pregnant woman gets to an ultrasound specialist when she is registered, then at 20 weeks, after that the examination becomes a monthly procedure;
- Dopplerography, fetometry are also performed every month after week 20;

From the 26th week, 2 times a month it is necessary to assess the condition of the fetus, uterus, therefore CTG is performed regularly; the geneticist, if necessary, prescribes additional cytogenetic examinations, a chorion biopsy.

Conclusions: thus, it is extremely important during this period to observe the daily routine, lack of stress, and proper nutrition. Treatment of epilepsy in pregnant women and prevention of seizures is carried out with the help of traditional anticonvulsants. A pregnant woman should avoid all factors that can provoke an attack. Clinical characteristics and pregnancy outcomes of new onset epilepsy during pregnancy. Li W, Hao N, Xiao Y, Zhou D. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2019 Jul; 98 (27): e16156. Therapeutic strategies for treating epilepsy during pregnancy.

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ЖУРНАЛ НЕВРОЛОГИИ И НЕЙРОХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

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